

Machine Learning Code Understanding

Investigating Machine Learning Code Understanding.

You will be asked to give your consent to participate in the research and will answer a set of questions involving: a brief characterization; questions about code comprehension; and a brief finalization.

The questionnaire takes around 20 minutes and your contribution will help us in the scientific advancement of software engineering for machine learning.

To thank you for your contribution, we will raffle 5 physical books on Software Engineering for Data Science among the survey respondents. Thank you for your cooperation!

1. E-mail *

Consent Form

This study aims to understand the impact of design principles on understanding machine learning code.

The research follows a high academic standard and is conducted anonymously. We will not associate your name or email address with your responses. In addition, you may request that your information be removed from this study at any time.

2. Name: *

3.

*

I declare my consent to participate in the research:

Marcar apenas uma oval.

Yes.

No.

Participants' characterization

4. 1) Highest level of education : *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

None.

Bachelor's Degree.

Post-Graduate Specialization.

Master's Degree.

Doctoral Degree.

5. 2) Do you have any academic degree related to computer science? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

Yes.

No.

6. 2.1) If yes, what ?

7. 3) What is your experience with software development? (More than one option can be selected) *

Marque todas que se aplicam.

- I have never developed software.
- I have been developing for my own use.
- I have been developing as team member, related to a course.
- I have been developing as team member, in industry.

8. 3.1) What is your experience with software development in years? *

9. 4) What is your experience with Machine Learning (ML) software development? (More than one option can be selected) *

Marque todas que se aplicam.

- I never developed ML software.
- I developed ML software for my own use.
- I developed ML software as a team member, related to a course.
- I developed ML software as a team member in the industry.

10. 4.1) What is your experience with Machine Learning software development in years? *

11. 5) Please, select for each topic the level of your experience following the 5 points scale (look at the subtitle):

*

Subtitle:

1 = No experience.

2 = I studied in a classroom or in a book.

3 = I actively practiced in a classroom project.

4 = I used it in one project in industry.

5 = I used it in several projects in industry.

Marcar apenas uma oval por linha.

	1	2	3	4	5
Object-oriented programming	<input type="radio"/>				
Encapsulation.	<input type="radio"/>				
Use of Inheritance, Abstract Classes and Interfaces.	<input type="radio"/>				
Clean Code.	<input type="radio"/>				
SOLID Principles.	<input type="radio"/>				
Design Patterns.	<input type="radio"/>				
Domain-Driven Design (DDD).	<input type="radio"/>				
Python language.	<input type="radio"/>				

12. 6) How do you rate your English reading and comprehension skills? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

Basic.

Intermediate.

Advanced.

Questionnaire

The Python code below aims to create a linear regression model using the Scikit-learn library to make predictions based on a dataset. The dataset is loaded from Azure ML Workspace and separated into training and test sets. Then, a linear regression model is created using the training data and evaluated with the test data, where the mean squared error (MSE) and the coefficient of determination (R^2) of the model are calculated. Finally, the model is used to make predictions and the results are plotted on a graph comparing predicted values with actual values.

Analyze the code:

```
1 import azureml.core
2 from azureml.core import Workspace
3
4 # Load the workspace from the saved config file
5 ws = Workspace.from_config()
6 print('Ready to use Azure ML {} to work with {}'.format(azureml.core.VERSION, ws.name))
7
8 print("This notebook was created using version 1.12.0 of the Azure ML SDK")
9 print("You are currently using version", azureml.core.VERSION, "of the Azure ML SDK")
10
11 # Get the default datastore
12 default_ds = ws.get_default_datastore()
13
14 # Enumerate all datastores, indicating which is the default
15 for ds_name in ws.datastores:
16     print(ds_name, "- Default =", ds_name == default_ds.name)
17
18 from azureml.core import Datastore
19
20 aml_datastore = Datastore.get(ws, 'revap_u220_pfenc')
21
22 print('Datastore:', aml_datastore.name)
23 print('Datastore type:', aml_datastore.datastore_type)
24 print('Container:', aml_datastore.container_name)
25 print('Storage Account:', aml_datastore.account_name)
26
27 ws.set_default_datastore('sandbox')
28 default_ds = ws.get_default_datastore()
29 print(default_ds.name)
30
31
```

```
1 import os
2 print("Path at terminal when executing this file")
3 print(os.getcwd())
4
5 train_ds = ws.datasets.get("revap-u220-pfenc-stream")
6 test_ds = ws.datasets.get("revap-u220-pfenc-test")
7 print("Data ready!")
8
9 # Display the first 5 rows as a Pandas dataframe
10 train_ds.take(5).to_pandas_dataframe()
11
12 # Display the first 5 rows as a Pandas dataframe
13 test_ds.take(5).to_pandas_dataframe()
14
15 # Import libraries
16 import pandas as pd
17 from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
18 from sklearn.linear_model import LinearRegression
19 from sklearn.metrics import mean_squared_error, r2_score
20 import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
21
22 train_df = train_ds.to_pandas_dataframe()
23 train_df.sort_index(inplace=True)
24 train_df.tail()
25
26 # Separate features and labels
27 X = train_df[['220NCPFEINF', 'PI 22068A0', '220CARGA/H', 'FC 22046PV', 'FI 22049A0', 'TI 22059A0', 'TC 22010PV']].values
28 y = train_df['AM264051BEN'].values
29
30 # Split data into training set and test set
31 X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(X, y, test_size=0.30, random_state=0)
32
33
```

```
1 # LinearRegression model
2 model = LinearRegression(normalize=True).fit(X_train, y_train)
3
4 # Predict
5 y_hat = model.predict(X_test)
6
7 # calculate mse
8 mse = mean_squared_error(y_test, y_hat)
9 print('MSE:', mse)
10
11 # calculate r2
12 r2 = r2_score(y_test, y_hat)
13 print('R2 score:', r2)
14
15 # plot
16 fig = plt.figure(figsize=(6, 4))
17 plt.plot(y_hat, "-b", label="y_hat")
18 plt.plot(y_test, "-r", label="y")
19 x1,x2,y1,y2 = plt.axis()
20 x1 = 0
21 x2 = 50
22 plt.axis((x1,x2,y1,y2))
23 plt.xlabel('Samples')
24 plt.ylabel('y and y_hat')
25 plt.title('y and y_hat comparison')
26 plt.legend(loc="upper left")
27 plt.show()
28
29
```

13. 1- What is your perception about understanding the source code? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

1 - Very hard.

2 - Hard.

3 - Normal.

4 - Easy.

5 - Very easy.

14. 2- What motivated your answer about understanding the code?

15. 3- The responsibilities in the code above are clearly distributed and defined. *
What is your degree of agreement with the statement?

Marcar apenas uma oval.

1- Totally disagree.

2- I disagree.

3- I neither agree nor disagree.

4- I agree.

5- Totally agree.

16. **4- Justify your answer about the degree of agreement.**

17. **5- The code block above is structured to have a single responsibility in the software, that is, it is specialized in a single subject. What is your degree of agreement with the statement?** *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- 1- Totally disagree.
- 2- I disagree.
- 3- I neither agree nor disagree.
- 4- I agree.
- 5- Totally agree.

18. **6- Justify your answer about the degree of agreement.**

19. **7- The code block above is structured to have a single reason for change. What is your degree of agreement with the statement?** *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- 1- Totally disagree.
- 2- I disagree.
- 3- I neither agree nor disagree.
- 4- I agree.
- 5- Totally agree.

20. **8- Justify your answer about the degree of agreement.**

From the analysis of model evaluation metrics, it was observed the need to test other regression algorithms to verify which one can be more effective for the available data set.

We are going to perform software maintenance to allow the use of Ridge Regression, Random Forest Regression and Support Vector Regression algorithms in regression predictions.

The code below creates instances of the Ridge, RandomForestRegressor and SVR classes. Soon after, it performs the training, makes predictions and evaluates the results of all available models.

Analyze the code:

```
1 # Import additional models
2 from sklearn.linear_model import Ridge
3 from sklearn.ensemble import RandomForestRegressor
4 from sklearn.svm import SVR
5
6 # Ridge Regression model
7 ridge = Ridge(alpha=1.0, normalize=True).fit(X_train, y_train)
8 y_hat_ridge = ridge.predict(X_test)
9 mse_ridge = mean_squared_error(y_test, y_hat_ridge)
10 r2_ridge = r2_score(y_test, y_hat_ridge)
11
12 # Random Forest Regression model
13 rfr = RandomForestRegressor(n_estimators=100, max_depth=10, random_state=0).fit(X_train, y_train)
14 y_hat_rfr = rfr.predict(X_test)
15 mse_rfr = mean_squared_error(y_test, y_hat_rfr)
16 r2_rfr = r2_score(y_test, y_hat_rfr)
17
18 # Support Vector Regression model
19 svr = SVR(kernel='linear', C=1.0, epsilon=0.2).fit(X_train, y_train)
20 y_hat_svr = svr.predict(X_test)
21 mse_svr = mean_squared_error(y_test, y_hat_svr)
22 r2_svr = r2_score(y_test, y_hat_svr)
23
24
```

```
1 # Print results
2 print('Linear Regression - MSE:', mse, 'R2 score:', r2)
3 print('Ridge Regression - MSE:', mse_ridge, 'R2 score:', r2_ridge)
4 print('Random Forest Regression - MSE:', mse_rfr, 'R2 score:', r2_rfr)
5 print('Support Vector Regression - MSE:', mse_svr, 'R2 score:', r2_svr)
6
7 # Plot
8 fig = plt.figure(figsize=(10, 6))
9 plt.plot(y_test, Label="y")
10 plt.plot(y_hat, Label="Linear Regression")
11 plt.plot(y_hat_ridge, Label="Ridge Regression")
12 plt.plot(y_hat_rfr, Label="Random Forest Regression")
13 plt.plot(y_hat_svr, Label="Support Vector Regression")
14 plt.xlabel('Samples')
15 plt.ylabel('y and y_hat')
16 plt.title('y and y_hat comparison')
17 plt.legend(Loc="upper left")
18 plt.show()
19
20
```

21. **9- What is your perception about understanding the source code? ***

Marcar apenas uma oval.

1 - Very hard.

2 - Hard.

3 - Normal.

4 - Easy.

5 - Very easy.

22. **10- What motivated your answer about understanding the code?**

23. **11- It was easy to extend the behavior of the software with the addition of new models. What is your degree of agreement with the statement? ***

Marcar apenas uma oval.

1- Totally disagree.

2- I disagree.

3- I neither agree nor disagree.

4- I agree.

5- Totally agree.

24. **12- Justify your answer about the degree of agreement.**

25. **13- Adding new models did not imply changing the pre-existing code. What is your degree of agreement with the statement? ***

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- 1- Totally disagree.
- 2- I disagree.
- 3- I neither agree nor disagree.
- 4- I agree.
- 5- Totally agree.

26. **14- Justify your answer about the degree of agreement.**

The plurality of regression models brings the need to run a list of models.

The code below adds the `processes_models` function to allow execution a list of models and shows an example run.

Analyze the code:

```
1 from sklearn.metrics import mean_squared_error, r2_score
2 import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
3
4
5 def processes_models(models:list,X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test):
6     for model in models:
7         model.fit(X_train, y_train)
8         y_hat= model.predict(X_test)
9         mse = mean_squared_error(y_test, y_hat)
10        print('MSE:', mse)
11        r2 = r2_score(y_test, y_hat)
12        print('R2 score:', r2)
13
14        # plot
15        fig = plt.figure(figsize=(6, 4))
16        plt.plot(y_hat,"-b", Label="y_hat")
17        plt.plot(y_test,"-r", Label="y")
18        x1,x2,y1,y2 = plt.axis()
19        x1 = 0
20        x2 = 50
21        plt.axis((x1,x2,y1,y2))
22        plt.xlabel('Samples')
23        plt.ylabel('y and y_hat')
24        plt.title('y and y_hat comparison')
25        plt.legend(Loc="upper left")
26        plt.show()
27
28
```

```
1 import azureml.core
2 from azureml.core import Workspace
3
4 # Load the workspace from the saved config file
5 ws = Workspace.from_config()
6 print('Ready to use Azure ML {} to work with {}'.format(azureml.core.VERSION, ws.name))
7
8 print("This notebook was created using version 1.12.0 of the Azure ML SDK")
9 print("You are currently using version", azureml.core.VERSION, "of the Azure ML SDK")
10
11 # Get the default datastore
12 default_ds = ws.get_default_datastore()
13
14 # Enumerate all datastores, indicating which is the default
15 for ds_name in ws.datastores:
16     print(ds_name, "- Default =", ds_name == default_ds.name)
17
18 from azureml.core import Datastore
19
20 aml_datastore = Datastore.get(ws, 'revap_u220_pfenc')
21
22 print('Datastore:', aml_datastore.name)
23 print('Datastore type:', aml_datastore.datastore_type)
24 print('Container:', aml_datastore.container_name)
25 print('Storage Account:', aml_datastore.account_name)
26
27 ws.set_default_datastore('sandbox')
28 default_ds = ws.get_default_datastore()
29 print(default_ds.name)
30
31 import os
32 print("Path at terminal when executing this file")
33 print(os.getcwd())
34
35 train_ds = ws.datasets.get("revap-u220-pfenc-stream")
36 test_ds = ws.datasets.get("revap-u220-pfenc-test")
37 print("Data ready!")
38
39 # Display the first 5 rows as a Pandas dataframe
40 train_ds.take(5).to_pandas_dataframe()
41
42 # Display the first 5 rows as a Pandas dataframe
43 test_ds.take(5).to_pandas_dataframe()
44
45
```

```
1 # Import libraries
2 import pandas as pd
3 from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
4 from sklearn.linear_model import LinearRegression
5 from sklearn.linear_model import Ridge
6 from sklearn.ensemble import RandomForestRegressor
7 from sklearn.svm import SVR
8
9
10 train_df = train_ds.to_pandas_dataframe()
11 train_df.sort_index(inplace=True)
12 train_df.tail()
13
14 # Separate features and labels
15 X = train_df[['220NCPFEINF', 'PI 22068AO', '220CARGA/H', 'FC 22046PV', 'FI 22049AO', 'TI 22059AO', 'TC 22010PV']].values
16 y = train_df['AM264051BEN'].values
17
18 # Split data into training set and test set
19 X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(X, y, test_size=0.30, random_state=0)
20
21 # Linear Regression model
22 linear = LinearRegression(normalize=True)
23 # Ridge Regression model
24 ridge = Ridge(alpha=1.0, normalize=True)
25 # Random Forest Regression model
26 rfr = RandomForestRegressor(n_estimators=100, random_state=0)
27 # Support Vector Regression model
28 svr = SVR(kernel='rbf', C= 100)
29
30 models = [linear,ridge,rfr,svr]
31
32 processes_models(models,X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test)
33
34
```

27. 15- What is your perception about understanding the source code? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- 1 - Very hard.
- 2 - Hard.
- 3 - Normal.
- 4 - Easy.
- 5 - Very easy.

28. 16- What motivated your answer about understanding the code?

29. **17- The models can be replaced without the need to change the `processes_models` function. What is your degree of agreement with the statement?** *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- 1- Totally disagree.
- 2- I disagree.
- 3- I neither agree nor disagree.
- 4- I agree.
- 5- Totally agree.

30. **18- Justify your answer about the degree of agreement.**

31. **19- Changes in a model implementation do not imply a change in the `processes_models` function. What is your degree of agreement with the statement?** *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- 1- Totally disagree.
- 2- I disagree.
- 3- I neither agree nor disagree.
- 4- I agree.
- 5- Totally agree.

32. **20- Justify your answer about the degree of agreement.**

Coupling, in software development, refers to the degree to which different components of a system are interconnected and dependent on each other. It is a measure of the dependency between modules or classes within a system. The higher the coupling, the greater the dependency between the components. Low coupling is desirable as it indicates that the parts of the system are independent and can be modified or replaced without affecting the entire system. This leads to more flexible, reusable and maintainable code.

33.

*

21- The processes_models function has loose coupling with model implementations. What is your degree of agreement with the statement?

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- 1- Totally disagree.
- 2- I disagree.
- 3- I neither agree nor disagree.
- 4- I agree.
- 5- Totally agree.

34. **22- Justify your answer about the degree of agreement.**

Exploratory data analysis shows that we can also solve a classification problem with the same dataset.

We are going to perform software maintenance to allow the use of Linear Support Vector Machines and Support Vector Machines algorithms in classification predictions.

The code below adds new instances of LinearSVC and SVC.

Analyze the code:

A terminal window with a dark background and three colored window control buttons (red, yellow, green) at the top left. The code is as follows:

```
1
2  from sklearn.svm import SVC
3  from sklearn.svm import LinearSVC
4
5  linear_svc = LinearSVC()
6  svc = SVC()
```

The inclusion of classification algorithms brings a new need, our model processing function is currently only able to evaluate regression algorithms.

The code below refactors the `processes_models` function by adding evaluation metrics for classification algorithms.

Analyze the code:

```
1 from sklearn.metrics import accuracy_score, precision_score, recall_score, f1_score
2 from sklearn.metrics import mean_squared_error, r2_score
3 import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
4
5
6 def processes_models(models:list,X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test):
7     for model in models:
8         model.fit(X_train, y_train)
9         y_hat= model.predict(X_test)
10        mse = mean_squared_error(y_test, y_hat)
11        print('MSE:', mse)
12        r2 = r2_score(y_test, y_hat)
13        print('R2 score:', r2)
14        accuracy = accuracy_score(y_test,y_hat)
15        print('Accuracy:',accuracy)
16        precision = precision_score(y_test,y_hat)
17        print('Precision:',precision)
18        recall = recall_score(y_test,y_hat)
19        print('Recall:',recall)
20        f1 = f1_score(y_test,y_hat)
21        print('F1-score:',f1)
22
23        # plot
24        fig = plt.figure(figsize=(6, 4))
25        plt.plot(y_hat,"-b", Label="y_hat")
26        plt.plot(y_test,"-r", Label="y")
27        x1,x2,y1,y2 = plt.axis()
28        x1 = 0
29        x2 = 50
30        plt.axis((x1,x2,y1,y2))
31        plt.xlabel('Samples')
32        plt.ylabel('y and y_hat')
33        plt.title('y and y_hat comparison')
34        plt.legend(Loc="upper left")
35        plt.show()
36
37
```

35. **23- What is your perception about understanding the source code? ***

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- 1 - Very hard.
- 2 - Hard.
- 3 - Normal.
- 4 - Easy.
- 5 - Very easy.

36. **24- What motivated your answer about understanding the code?**

37. **25- Metrics are properly segregated for evaluation of classification and regression algorithms. What is your degree of agreement with the statement?** *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- 1- Totally disagree.
- 2- I disagree.
- 3- I neither agree nor disagree.
- 4- I agree.
- 5- Totally agree.

38. **26- Justify your answer about the degree of agreement.**

Having distinct evaluation metrics implies selecting the correct metrics for evaluation by classification and regression algorithms.

The code below refactors the `processes_models` function by adding the `type_of_metrics` argument, which indicates whether the evaluation will be done with regression or classification metrics. Where the 'c' value represents classification metrics and the 'r' value represents regression metrics.

Analyze the code:

```
1 def processes_models(models:list,X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test,type_of_metrics):
2     for model in models:
3         model.fit(X_train, y_train)
4         y_hat= model.predict(X_test)
5         mse = mean_squared_error(y_test, y_hat)
6         #r - regression algorithms
7         if(type_of_metrics == 'r'):
8             print('MSE:', mse)
9             r2 = r2_score(y_test, y_hat)
10            print('R2 score:', r2)
11            #c - classification algorithms
12            elif(type_of_metrics == 'c'):
13                accuracy = accuracy_score(y_test,y_hat)
14                print('Accuracy:',accuracy)
15                precision = precision_score(y_test,y_hat)
16                print('Precision:',precision)
17                recall = recall_score(y_test,y_hat)
18                print('Recall:',recall)
19                f1 = f1_score(y_test,y_hat)
20                print('F1-score:',f1)
21
22            # plot
23            fig = plt.figure(figsize=(6, 4))
24            plt.plot(y_hat,"-b", Label="y_hat")
25            plt.plot(y_test,"-r", Label="y")
26            x1,x2,y1,y2 = plt.axis()
27            x1 = 0
28            x2 = 50
29            plt.axis((x1,x2,y1,y2))
30            plt.xlabel('Samples')
31            plt.ylabel('y and y_hat')
32            plt.title('y and y_hat comparison')
33            plt.legend(Loc="upper left")
34            plt.show()
35
36
```

39. 27- What is your perception about understanding the source code? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- 1 - Very hard.
- 2 - Hard.
- 3 - Normal.
- 4 - Easy.
- 5 - Very easy.

40. **28- What motivated your answer about understanding the code?**

The current code of the `processes_models` function requires that all algorithms are regression or classification for a correct evaluation of the algorithm.

In order to have one type of metric per algorithm, let's refactor the `processes_models` function to receive a list of algorithms with the mapping for their respective type of metric to be evaluated.

Analyze the code:

```
1 def processes_models(models_with_metric:list,X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test):
2     for i in models_with_metric:
3         model = i[0]
4         type_of_metrics = i[1]
5         model.fit(X_train, y_train)
6         y_hat= model.predict(X_test)
7         mse = mean_squared_error(y_test, y_hat)
8         #r - regression algorithms
9         if(type_of_metrics == 'r'):
10            print('MSE:', mse)
11            r2 = r2_score(y_test, y_hat)
12            print('R2 score:', r2)
13        #c - classification algorithms
14        elif(type_of_metrics == 'c'):
15            accuracy = accuracy_score(y_test,y_hat)
16            print('Accuracy:',accuracy)
17            precision = precision_score(y_test,y_hat)
18            print('Precision:',precision)
19            recall = recall_score(y_test,y_hat)
20            print('Recall:',recall)
21            f1 = f1_score(y_test,y_hat)
22            print('F1-score:',f1)
23
24        # plot
25        fig = plt.figure(figsize=(6, 4))
26        plt.plot(y_hat,"-b", Label="y_hat")
27        plt.plot(y_test,"-r", Label="y")
28        x1,x2,y1,y2 = plt.axis()
29        x1 = 0
30        x2 = 50
31        plt.axis((x1,x2,y1,y2))
32        plt.xlabel('Samples')
33        plt.ylabel('y and y_hat')
34        plt.title('y and y_hat comparison')
35        plt.legend(Loc="upper left")
36        plt.show()
37
38
```

41. **29- What is your perception about understanding the source code? ***

Marcar apenas uma oval.

1 - Very hard.

2 - Hard.

3 - Normal.

4 - Easy.

5 - Very easy.

42. **30- What motivated your answer about understanding the code?**

The code below creates a variable with the mapping of models with their respective evaluation metric type and shows an example of executing the processes_models function.

Analyze the code:

```
1 from sklearn.linear_model import LinearRegression
2 from sklearn.linear_model import Ridge
3 from sklearn.ensemble import RandomForestRegressor
4 from sklearn.svm import SVR
5 from sklearn.svm import LinearSVC
6 from sklearn.svm import SVC
7
8 # Linear Regression model
9 linear = LinearRegression(normalize=True)
10 # Ridge Regression model
11 ridge = Ridge(alpha=1.0, normalize=True)
12 # Random Forest Regression model
13 rfr = RandomForestRegressor(n_estimators=100, random_state=0)
14 # Support Vector Regression model
15 svr = SVR(kernel='rbf', C= 100)
16 # Linear Support Vector Machines model
17 linear_svc = LinearSVC()
18 # Support Vector Machines Model
19 svc = SVC()
20
21 models_with_metric = [
22     [linear, 'r'],
23     [ridge, 'r'],
24     [rfr, 'r'],
25     [svr, 'r'],
26     [linear_svc, 'c'],
27     [svc, 'c']
28 ]
29
30
```

```
1 import azureml.core
2 from azureml.core import Workspace
3
4 # Load the workspace from the saved config file
5 ws = Workspace.from_config()
6 print('Ready to use Azure ML {} to work with {}'.format(azureml.core.VERSION, ws.name))
7
8 print("This notebook was created using version 1.12.0 of the Azure ML SDK")
9 print("You are currently using version", azureml.core.VERSION, "of the Azure ML SDK")
10
11 # Get the default datastore
12 default_ds = ws.get_default_datastore()
13
14 # Enumerate all datastores, indicating which is the default
15 for ds_name in ws.datastores:
16     print(ds_name, "- Default =", ds_name == default_ds.name)
17
18 from azureml.core import Datastore
19
20 aml_datastore = Datastore.get(ws, 'revap_u220_pfenc')
21
22 print('Datastore:', aml_datastore.name)
23 print('Datastore type:', aml_datastore.datastore_type)
24 print('Container:', aml_datastore.container_name)
25 print('Storage Account:', aml_datastore.account_name)
26
27 ws.set_default_datastore('sandbox')
28 default_ds = ws.get_default_datastore()
29 print(default_ds.name)
30
31
```

```
1 import os
2 print("Path at terminal when executing this file")
3 print(os.getcwd())
4
5 train_ds = ws.datasets.get("revap-u220-pfenc-stream")
6 test_ds = ws.datasets.get("revap-u220-pfenc-test")
7 print("Data ready!")
8
9 # Display the first 5 rows as a Pandas dataframe
10 train_ds.take(5).to_pandas_dataframe()
11
12 # Display the first 5 rows as a Pandas dataframe
13 test_ds.take(5).to_pandas_dataframe()
14
15 # Import libraries
16 import pandas as pd
17 from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
18
19 train_df = train_ds.to_pandas_dataframe()
20 train_df.sort_index(inplace=True)
21 train_df.tail()
22
23 # Separate features and labels
24 X = train_df[['220NCPFEINF', 'PI 22068A0', '220CARGA/H', 'FC 22046PV', 'FI 22049A0', 'TI 22059A0', 'TC 22010PV']].values
25 y = train_df['AM264051BEN'].values
26
27 # Split data into training set and test set
28 X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(X, y, test_size=0.30, random_state=0)
29
30 processes_models(models_with_metric,X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test)
31
32
```

43. 31- What is your perception about understanding the source code? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- 1 - Very hard.
- 2 - Hard.
- 3 - Normal.
- 4 - Easy.
- 5 - Very easy.

44. 32- What motivated your answer about the complexity of the code?

Finalization

45. 1) What good practices do you think would help understanding machine learning code? *

46. 2) Do you have any other suggestions to improve understanding of machine learning code?

47. 3) Are you available to answer a few more questions? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

Yes.

No.

Google Formulários

